

www.arseam.com

NEEDS OF “HRD CONCEPT” IN BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

Dr. Manoj Kumar Sharma
Lecturer,
Dept of Bus. Admin.
S.P.U.(PG) College, Falna
Distt- Pali (Rajasthan), India

ABSTRACT

HRD is needed by any organisation that wants to be dynamic and growth-oriented or to succeed in a fast-changing environment. Organisations can become dynamic and grow only through the efforts and competencies of their human resources. Personnel policies can keep the morale and motivation of employees high, but these efforts are not enough to make the organisation dynamic and take it in new directions. Employee capabilities must continuously be acquired, sharpened, and used. For this purpose, an “enabling” organisational culture is essential. Even an organisation that has reached its limit of growth, needs to adapt to the changing environment. No organisation is immune to the need for processes that help to acquire and increase its capabilities for stability and renewal.

Key words: Concept, Function, Learning

INTRODUCTION:

MEANING OF HRM:

Human Resource Development is the part of human resource management that specifically deals with training and development of the employees in The organization. Human resource development includes training a person after he or she is first hired, providing opportunities to learn new skills, distributing resources that are beneficial for the employee's tasks, and any other developmental activities.

DEFINITION OF HRM:

Development of human resources is essential for any organisation that would like to be dynamic and growth-oriented. Unlike other resources, human resources have rather unlimited potential capabilities. The potential can be used only by creating a climate that can continuously identify, bring to surface, nurture and use the capabilities of people. Human Resource Development

(HRD) system aims at creating such a climate. A number of HRD techniques have been developed in recent years to perform the above task based on certain principles. This unit provides an understanding of the concept of HRD system, related mechanisms and the changing Boundaries of HRD.

HRD concept was first introduced by Leonard Nadler in 1969 in a conference in US. “He defined HRD as those learning experience which are organized, for a specific time, and designed to bring about the Possibility of behavioural change”.

Human Resource Development (HRD) is the framework for helping employees develop their personal and organizational skills, knowledge, and abilities. Human Resource Development includes such opportunities as employee training, employee career development, performance management and development, coaching, mentoring, succession planning, key employee identification, tuition assistance, and organization development. The focus of all aspects of Human Resource Development is on developing the most superior workforce so that the organization and individual employees can accomplish their work goals in service to customers.

THE CONCEPT OF HRD:

Human resource development in the organisation context is a process by which the employees of an organisation are helped, in a continuous and planned way to:

1. Acquire or sharpen capabilities required to perform various functions associated with their present or expected future roles;
2. Develop their general capabilities as individuals and discover and exploit their own inner potentials for their own and/or organisational development purposes; and
3. Develop an organisational culture in which supervisor-subordinate relationships, teamwork and collaboration among sub-units are strong and contribute to the professional well being, motivation and pride of employees.

HRD is a process, not merely a set of mechanisms and techniques. The mechanisms and techniques such as performance appraisal, counseling, training, and organization development

interventions are used to initiate, facilitate, and promote this process in a continuous way. Because the process has no limit, the mechanisms may need to be examined periodically to see whether they are promoting or hindering the process. Organisations can facilitate this process of development by planning for it, by allocating organisational resources for the purpose, and by exemplifying an HRD philosophy that values human beings and promotes their development.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT?:

Human resources development can be viewed, in some ways, in the same manner that a coach views his athletic team. While a coach may recruit players who already have some skill and ability, the point of continued practice is to strengthen those skills and abilities and make even better athletes. HR development has the same goal: to make better employees. The purpose of HR development is to provide the 'coaching' needed to strengthen and grow the knowledge, skills, and abilities that an employee already has. The goal of development and training is to make employees even better at what they do.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HR & HRD FUNCTIONS IN A LARGE ORGANIZATION:

The work of human resources departments encompasses a wide range of functions, and large organizations may have many HR professionals on staff. Generally HR functions are split into two broad categories. One, usually called HR management, or just HR, is concerned with the day-to-day operation of a company. HR development, or HRD, has a more forward-looking role.

HRM

The types of tasks that might come under the human resources management category include compensation, payroll issues, benefits management and day-to-day employee relations. Human resources professionals from this category would be involved in any dispute that an employee has with management. They would also be involved in hiring and firing. These types of tasks can be described as routine and administrative.

HRD

By contrast, human resources development concerns itself with strategic thinking about the workforce. Therefore training needs, industrial psychology and driving productivity gains would all be the province of HRD. Professionals working in this area do sometimes concern themselves with the individuals’ needs in an organization, but they more often consider the workforce needs of the company as a whole.

LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN COMPANIES

Companies and institutions invest billions in education and training. Large companies often have their own corporate department for HR development and offer training to improve staff performance and professional development. As an HRD graduate, you will be able to develop and implement such training and to assess its quality. You might also be engaged in workplace learning or organizational change aimed at making learning an integral part of the day-to-day work environment.

WHAT IS THE FUNCTION OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT?:

The function of human resource development is to **improve performance and ability**. While employees are often expected to know a certain amount about their jobs or have a specific degree or level of education upon hire, much of what an employee learns about their job is developed over the course of doing the job. This development includes specific organizational knowledge or job-specific duties that are not necessarily taught in the classroom.

Regardless of the form the development takes, it functions as a means to improve the overall performance and ability of employees in the jobs they are doing as well as in future positions. Human resource development can function to improve performance or individual abilities in an area in which an employee is weak (such as management skills or accounting practices). It can also function to teach an employee about an area in which the employee has had no prior experience, such as when transitioning from one role into a different role (i.e., cross-training).

HR development may also function to help an organization conform to government regulations or guidelines by training employees on relevant laws or regulations for which they are responsible. It may also take the form of professional development by educating in specific areas or fields. The Professional in Human Resources certification, Project Management Professional certification, and Six Sigma Black Belt are examples of courses and certifications designed to train and develop professionals in these specific fields.

EXAMPLES OF HUMAN RESOURCES DEVELOPMENT:

Human resources development usually begins as soon as an employee is hired and continues throughout that employee's tenure with the organization. HRD comes in different forms, including on-the-job training or job shadowing, textbook or online education, growth opportunities, and compliance training. **On-the-job training** refers to learning the aspects of a job while one is doing the job. An employee may know the basics of what the job requires, but specifics like which forms to use, where materials are stored, and how to access the computer systems may require on-the-job training. **Job shadowing** is similar in that you watch another employee do the job in order to develop the proper skills.

Another form of development is **intellectual or professional development**, which includes college or certification courses or job-specific trainings and seminars related to how to do one's job better. Many organizations invest heavily in providing training and development to their employees in order to increase their knowledge and skills. With the growth of online learning, much of this training has become available via webinars and online courses, but it is still very common to conduct in-person trainings or attend training seminars or conferences with other professionals in the field.

LIFELONG LEARNING: THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT WITHIN ORGANISATIONS:

1. The “learning organisation” is an important metaphor for HRD professionals to assist them in:

- a) Developing collective intelligence within organisations and organisational forms supporting such a need thus eliminating the holding of knowledge in separate compartments at different levels.
 - b) Understanding the importance of knowledge and in particular tacit knowledge, which has to be recognised and valorised insofar as it is embedded in human resources.
 - c) Moving from training-based development policies towards new policies fostering learning in different ways (support for competencies development, learning networks, learning self-assessment in the communities of practice).
2. Learning oriented organisations do employ a rich bouquet of change initiatives, in which, no one type of change is particularly dominant.
 3. The main motivator for wanting to become a learning organisation is the desire to become more client centered by continuous improvement and innovation. However, more people-oriented reasons such as improving the quality of working life seem to play a role as well.
 4. The envisioned role of HRD professionals within learning organisations is to: -
 - a) Support the business.
 - b) Support (informal) learning.
 - c) Support knowledge sharing (as a special form of supporting informal learning).
 - d) Develop and coordinate training.
 - e) Change HRD practices.

REFERANCES:

BOOK:

Amstrong M. (2006) Human Resource Management Practices, 10thedition, Kogan PageLimited.

Abrahm, E; ‘HRD climate in banks’, Oxford and IBH publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1988

Chen, H., and Hung, S., ‘Systematic linking of organizational strategy, HR strategy and training strategy across OLC’, International Journal of business strategy.

Dyal, Ishwar., ‘HRD in Indian organizations : current perspectives and Future issues;’, Vikalpa

Luthans F. (1995),Organizational Behavior , 9thedition, New Delhi, Prentice hall of India Pvt Ltd.

Sheikh A.M (2007)., Human Resource development and Management, 2ndEdition, S.Chand Limited

www.whatishumanresource.com

<http://www.pjb.co.uk/npl/index.htm>